

DETERMINATION OF THE POSITION SOLAR MODULES USING UAV PHOTOGRAMMETRY AND COMPUTER VISION

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Abstract: *Solar modules are crucial in renewable energy production, especially in large-scale solar farms. Precise spatial location of individual modules is essential for monitoring, maintenance and detection of potential damage. This study combines Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV) photogrammetry and computer vision techniques to determine the 3D coordinates of solar modules. An UAV equipped with RGB and thermal cameras captured the area of interest. The You Only Look Once (YOLO) algorithm was used to automatically detect modules in thermal images, and the same modules were tracked across multiple images by applying keypoint matching and homography estimation in order to determine coordinates.*

Keywords: *Photogrammetry, Computer vision, YOLO, UAV, Thermal images, Solar Farm.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Solar farms involve the installation of a large number of solar modules in one place, with the aim of capturing solar energy and converting it into electricity. The electricity produced in this way is fed directly into the power grid and serves the electrical needs of local buildings, homes and larger facilities, industries, companies, etc. Increasing support for the development of solar modules is expected, in line with the European Green Deal initiative. This initiative aims to make Europe a climate-neutral continent by 2050. One of the envisaged strategies is exactly the use of renewable energy sources, including solar farms, in order to stop using fossil fuels (European Commission, 2019).

An UAV is a part of UAS (Unmanned Aerial System) that usually consists of an aircraft platform mounted with one or more sensors combined with a ground-based control station from where it is operated. An aerial platform is a basic component that carries with it various sensors and devices that enable safe flight of the aircraft and data collection. It contains an engine that provides flight, a Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS) antenna and an Inertial measurement unit (IMU) that can determine the position and orientation of the aircraft at any time, a battery that powers all electronic components during the aircraft flight and camera that collects high-resolution images and videos (Marković et al., 2021). In general, UAVs can be equipped with different types of sensors (RGB, thermal, multispectral, LiDAR) (E. J. Lee et al., 2016; Morales et al., 2020; Speth et al., 2022). Thermal camera uses the information at the emitted radiation in the thermal infrared range of the electromagnetic spectrum and converts this information into temperature. In such way it is possible to easily detect solar modules (Messina & Modica, 2020).

The concept of UAV imaging and photogrammetry involves firstly to define the area of interest, and based on that, to create a flight plan. During the flight, the UAV continuously collects images and records measured data from other mounted sensors such as GNSS, IMU and stores them in Exchangeable Image Format (EXIF). The key thing in the application of the photogrammetric method is to collect successive images with an appropriate overlap between them. It is this overlap that allows the processing of the collected images in order to create a three-dimensional model of the captured area.

Object detection is a kind of image segmentation based on object geometric and statistical features, also known as object extraction. One of the most commonly used object detection method, in case of UAV photogrammetry, is YOLO. This method completely abandons the detection mode of "region candidate + regression" in the two stages, and hence, this is what makes this method very fast and suitable for near real-

time object detection based on UAV images. YOLO scales the image to be measured into a uniform size and divides it into multiple grids, then predicts the target category according to the grid where the target center is located, and outputs the detection results on the last convolution layer. The core idea of YOLO is to transform target detection into a regression problem, using the whole image as the input of the network, and just through a neural network, the location of the bounding box and its category can be obtained (Cong et al., 2023; Krishna et al., 2021).

2. DATA AND METHODS

This chapter presents the entire start-to-end process, from collecting UAV imagery to forming a mathematical model for determine three-dimensional module coordinates based on two-dimensional measurements. For clarity, each element in this process, such as workflow overview, UAV configuration, camera orientation parameters, YOLO detection, and planar homography estimation, is covered in a separate subsection.

2.1. Workflow Overview

As illustrated in Figure 1, the workflow proceeds in the following stages. First, the UAV acquires thermal images and records an EXIF file containing GNSS and IMU-based position metadata. Second, the YOLO model is applied to the thermal frames to define a bounding box for each module. Third, the feature points extracted from the overlapping images provide the point pairs needed to estimate the planar homography. Finally, these two-dimensional observations from multiple views, along with internal and external orientation parameters, are input into a triangulation process that determines the three-dimensional coordinates of all modules.

Figure 1: Workflow for determining the position of solar modules

2.2. UAV Platform and Flight Configuration

The research was conducted in Brazil on a 143 ha solar farm using the DJI Mavic 3 Thermal (Global Power Generation, 2018). The aircraft provides up to 45 minutes of flight, enough to cover solar farms of approximately 200 ha in one go at an altitude of 40 meters. The specifications of the UAV can be found in Table 1. The solar farm was surveyed with front overlap of 80% and 60%, and side overlap of 60% and 45% for RGB and thermal images, respectively, at an altitude of 40 meters. A total of 436 RGB and 436 thermal images were collected.

Table 1: Key specifications of the DJI M3T (dji, 2024.)

Parameter	Specification
Weight (with propellers)	920 g
Max flight time (no wind)	45 min
Wide camera	1/2-inch CMOS, Effective pixels: 48 MP
Tele camera	1/2-inch CMOS, Effective pixels: 12 MP
Thermal camera	Uncooled VOx microbolometer; 640 × 512 px @ 30 Hz
GNSS	GPS, Galileo, BeiDou (GLONASS supported with RTK)

2.3. EXIF Metadata and Camera Orientation Parameters

Metadata for each image are included in EXIF file using a UAV equipped with GNSS/IMU sensors. The file contains the parameters of internal orientation (the intrinsic matrix \mathbf{K}) and external orientation (rotation matrix \mathbf{R} and translation vector \mathbf{t}), as well as additional information such as image dimensions, acquisition time, etc. (Verykokou & Ioannidis, 2016). The mathematical representation of the said matrices is as follows:

$$\mathbf{K} = \begin{bmatrix} f_x & s & c_x \\ 0 & f_y & c_y \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} f_x & 0 & c_x \\ 0 & f_y & c_y \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (1)$$

where f_x and f_y represents focal length, c_x and c_y represent the principal point and s represents skew. The rotation matrix \mathbf{R} is equivalent to the following formulations:

$$\mathbf{R} = \mathbf{R}_\omega * \mathbf{R}_\varphi * \mathbf{R}_\kappa = \begin{bmatrix} r_{11} & r_{12} & r_{13} \\ r_{21} & r_{22} & r_{23} \\ r_{31} & r_{32} & r_{33} \end{bmatrix} = \quad (2)$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} \cos(\varphi)\cos(\kappa) & -\cos(\varphi)\sin(\kappa) & \sin(\varphi) \\ \cos(\omega)\sin(\kappa) + \sin(\omega)\sin(\varphi)\cos(\kappa) & \cos(\omega)\cos(\kappa) - \sin(\omega)\sin(\varphi)\sin(\kappa) & -\sin(\omega)\cos(\varphi) \\ \sin(\omega)\sin(\kappa) - \cos(\omega)\sin(\varphi)\cos(\kappa) & \sin(\omega)\cos(\kappa) + \cos(\omega)\sin(\varphi)\sin(\kappa) & \cos(\omega)\cos(\varphi) \end{bmatrix},$$

where ω , φ , and κ are the Euler angles of rotation around X, Y and Z axis, and $\mathbf{R}_\omega, \mathbf{R}_\varphi, \mathbf{R}_\kappa$ denote the corresponding axis aligned rotation matrices. The vector \mathbf{t} represents the translational (positional) vector of the camera, i.e. the three-dimensional coordinate of the projection centre in the global coordinate system. Its components define how much the coordinate origin is shifted relative to the reference coordinate system and are expressed by the formula:

$$\mathbf{t} = \begin{bmatrix} t_x \\ t_y \\ t_z \end{bmatrix}, \quad (3)$$

where t_x , t_y and t_z denote the camera-centre coordinates along the X, Y and Z axes.

2.4. Module Detection with YOLOv8

One of the widely used artificial intelligence and computer vision methods for object detection in images is the YOLO (Ultralytics YOLO8, 2024). The original YOLO model processes the entire image in a single pass through a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) and can achieve real-time detection, which has made it the standard for UAV applications (Joseph Redmon et al., 2016). By introducing an anchor-free detection head, YOLOv8 directly regresses box coordinates and objectness scores without requiring manually defined anchors, which reduces the number of hyperparameters and speeds up model configuration (Ali & Zhang, 2024). The modifications to the YOLOv8 method lead to significant improvements in detection reliability, making it ideal for real-time applications in various areas of computer vision. Figure 2 illustrates an example of the YOLO algorithm applied for object detection in an image.

Figure 2: Example of operation of Darknet YOLO (Kanehisa & Neto, 2019)

2.5. Planar Homography Estimation

When two cameras observe the same physical plane from different viewpoints, their images are related by a unique 3×3 projective transformation called homography. This matrix compactly encodes the full

perspective warp (combining rotation, translation, scaling, shearing and foreshortening) and is the cornerstone of tasks such as image rectification, mosaicking and planar 3D reconstruction. The homography matrix \mathbf{H} defines a projective transformation between two overlapping images. It establishes a geometric relationship that maps points from one image to the corresponding points in the other (2D to 2D point correspondences). Estimating of planar homography matrix \mathbf{H} using the Direct Linear Transform (DLT) method (Hartley & Zisserman, 2004), is based on the keypoints detected on both images with scale-invariant feature transform (SIFT) algorithm (Lowe, 2004). The matrix \mathbf{H} represents a wide range of geometric transformations, including rotation, translation, scaling, shearing, and perspective distortion, all combined within a single 3×3 matrix (Hartley & Zisserman, 2004). Homography describes the transformation using the following Equation 4 as in the example in Figure 3:

$$\tilde{x}' = [\tilde{\mathbf{H}}]_{3 \times 3} \tilde{x}, \quad (4)$$

where \tilde{x} denotes a point in the first image, $\tilde{\mathbf{H}} \in \mathbf{R}^{3 \times 3}$ is the homography matrix, and \tilde{x}' denotes the corresponding point in the second image.

Figure 3: Illustration of the planar homography (Hartley & Zisserman, 2004)

In this way, two independent projections of the same object (in this case, a module) are obtained and a condition for further 3D reconstruction. The intersection of rays using the triangulation method yields a 3D coordinate, a standard procedure in multi-view photogrammetry (Hartley & Zisserman, 2004). The complete calculation of 3D coordinates in the global coordinate system using 2D measurements in the images is described by Equation 5:

$$\begin{bmatrix} X_s \\ Y_s \\ Z_s \end{bmatrix} = \mathbf{R} \begin{bmatrix} \frac{(u-c_x)*Z}{f_x} \\ \frac{(v-c_y)*Z}{f_x} \\ Z \end{bmatrix} + \mathbf{t}, \quad (5)$$

where u and v are the 2D coordinates of the point in images (measured values), Z is the point depth (distance from camera center to 3D point), f_x , c_x and c_y are the intrinsic camera parameters, \mathbf{R} and \mathbf{t} denote the rotation matrix and translation vector (camera center) in the global coordinate system, and $(X_s, Y_s, Z_s)^T$ are the final 3D coordinates of a point in the global coordinate system (unknown values).

From the Equation 5, the unknown values are the 3D coordinates, while the measured data are the corresponding 2D image coordinates u and v . In order to solve for the three unknowns the same point must be detected in at least two images taken from different viewpoints. This requirement arises because a single 2D observation constrains the 3D point to lie along a ray; the intersection of at least two such rays (from different camera positions) is necessary to compute the 3D location through triangulation.

3. RESULTS

Using a trained YOLO object detection model, individual solar module were detected in all thermal images, as illustrated in Figure 4. The output from the YOLO detection process was saved in a .json file, where the bounding boxes are encoded using normalised coordinates relative to the image dimensions (ranging from 0 to 1), with the top-left corner as the origin. This method provides only the 2D coordinates of the bounding box corners, but its format facilitates automated processing and seamless integration into Geographic information system (GIS) workflow systems (Ultralytics YOLO8, 2024).

After detecting the modules in the thermal images, keypoints were extracted from all images using the SIFT algorithm. Each image was matched with its two nearest neighbours (those with the highest overlap) and homography matrices were computed using feature matching techniques. Once established, these homography matrices can be used to correspond any pixel from between two images, effectively enabling the localisation of the same object in multiple views. By identifying the same object in three overlapping

images, a total of six 2D measurements (two per image) are obtained, which is sufficient to compute the 3D coordinates of the object using triangulation.

Figure 4: Thermal images with detected bounding box of solar farm

Using Equation 5, the 3D coordinates of each solar module were calculated and written in the .json file originally generated by the YOLO object detection algorithm. As a result, the final .json file contains the 2D coordinates of the four bounding box corners, corresponding latitude and longitude coordinates for each of those four points, and the coordinates of the module centre, as illustrated in Figure 5.

This approach enables the extraction of each module’s coordinates with satisfactory accuracy without the need for time-consuming processes such as aligning all images, generating a digital surface model, and creating an orthophoto for the entire area (a processing pipeline that can be particularly slow when dealing with a large number of images). Based on the obtained coordinates, further analyses and measurements can be performed on the modules, such as detecting tracker deformation caused by damaged support structures, calculating the width and height of solar modules in the 3D coordinate system, and easily locating individual modules in the field by exporting their coordinates to a KMZ file or similar formats.

```
{
  "TagId": "77834cd9-66af-414c-b1f3-67beb950034b",
  "Name": "module",
  "Confidence": 0.99912983,
  "Coordinates": {
    "Center": "-18.828124703669985, -46.676876700640044",
    "TopLeft": "-18.828129170515663, -46.676885457448",
    "TopRight": "-18.82812047007784, -46.676885585755485",
    "BottomLeft": "-18.82812893064024, -46.67686783832317",
    "BottomRight": "-18.828120243841486, -46.67686796631655"
  },
  "BoundingBox": {
    "Top": 0.38172325,
    "Left": 0,
    "Width": 0.8378141,
    "Height": 0.19233504
  }
},
"ThermalImage": "AEROID250312100353T-DJI_20250312100353_0006_T.JPG"
```

Figure 5: Example of final JSON file

5. CONCLUSION

The paper presents the application of photogrammetry and computer vision for the purposes of detection and determination of the coordinates of each solar module. As mentioned, the computer vision method itself detects modules in a local coordinate system, in the form of two-dimensional images. By integrating with photogrammetry, georeferencing is enabled, i.e., the determination of the actual spatial coordinates of the modules in the desired coordinate system. The method presented in the paper has proven to be very practical in the case of large solar farms, where a large number of images is collected. Thermal cameras have a smaller field of view compared to RGB cameras, so the only prerequisite is that the thermal images are collected with a large overlap, so that the modules can be identified using the detection algorithms. Otherwise, in the case of a smaller overlap, the processing would be very long and difficult. In general, the use of thermal cameras provides much more information in this case and allows for the use of more object detection methods than RGB cameras. In addition, on thermal images, it is possible to detect damage on the modules using computer vision algorithms and photogrammetry. Hence, by using the presented method, it is possible to extract the coordinates of damaged modules, which greatly reduces the time in the office required to detect damaged modules, as well as the time until these modules are found in the field.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This research has been supported by the Ministry of Science, Technological Development and Innovation (Contract No. 451-03-137/2025-03/200156) and the Faculty of Technical Sciences, University of Novi Sad through project “Scientific and Artistic Research Work of Researchers in Teaching and Associate Positions at the Faculty of Technical Sciences, University of Novi Sad 2025” (No. 01-50/295).

This paper is supported by Ministry of Science, Technological Development and Innovation of the Republic of Serbia (451-03-137/2025-03/200117).

LITERATURE

- Ali, M. L., & Zhang, Z. (2024). The YOLO Framework: A Comprehensive Review of Evolution, Applications, and Benchmarks in Object Detection. *Computers*, 13(12), 336. <https://doi.org/10.3390/computers13120336>.
- Cong, X., Li, S., Chen, F., Liu, C., & Meng, Y. (2023). A Review of YOLO Object Detection Algorithms based on Deep Learning. *Frontiers in Computing and Intelligent Systems*, 4(2), 17-20. <https://doi.org/10.54097/fcis.v4i2.9730>.
- dji. (2024). Specifications of the DJI Mavic 3T. Retrieved May 11, 2025, from <https://enterprise.dji.com/mavic-3-enterprise/specs>.
- The European Green Deal (2019), https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/priorities-2019-2024/european-green-deal_en, accessed on 13th May 2025.
- Global Power Generation. (2018). <https://ippjournal.com/project/82-5-mw-guimarania-solar-project-in-minas-gerais>, accessed on 03th August 2025.
- Hartley, R., & Zisserman, A. (2004). Multiple View Geometry in Computer Vision (2nd ed.). *Cambridge University Press*. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9780511811685>.
- Kanehisa, R., & Neto, A. (2019). Firearm Detection using Convolutional Neural Networks. *Proceedings of the 11th International Conference on Agents and Artificial Intelligence*, 707–714. <https://doi.org/10.5220/0007397707070714>.
- Krishna, N.M., Reddy, R.Y., Reddy, M.S.C., Madhav, K.P. & Sudham, G. (2021). Object Detection and Tracking Using Yolo. *Third International Conference on Inventive Research in Computing Applications (ICIRCA)*, Coimbatore, India, 2021, 1-7, doi: 10.1109/ICIRCA51532.2021.9544598.
- Lee, E. J., Shin, S. Y., Ko, B. C., & Chang, C. (2016). Early sinkhole detection using a drone-based thermal camera and image processing. *Infrared Physics & Technology*, 78, 223–232. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.infrared.2016.08.009>.
- Lopez-Franco, C., Fink, G., Arana-Daniel, N., & Alanis, A. Y. (2011). A visual servo control based on geometric algebra. *2011 8th International Conference on Electrical Engineering, Computing Science and Automatic Control*, 1–6. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICEEE.2011.6106633>.
- Lowe, D. G. (2004). Distinctive Image Features from Scale-Invariant Keypoints. *International Journal of Computer Vision*, 60(2), 91–110. <https://doi.org/10.1023/B:VISI.0000029664.99615.94>.
- Marković, M., Budimirov, T., Batilović, M., Bulatović, V. & Sušić, Z. (2021). Influence analysis of the number and distribution of control points on the quality of data collected by UAV. *iNDiS 2021 – Planninh, design, construction and building renewal*, Novi Sad, Republic of Serbia, 24-26th November 2021, 420-427.
- Messina, G., & Modica, G. (2020). Applications of UAV Thermal Imagery in Precision Agriculture: State of the Art and Future Research Outlook. *Remote Sensing*, 12(9), 1491. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs12091491>.
- Morales, A., Guerra, R., Horstrand, P., Diaz, M., Jimenez, A., Melian, J., Lopez, S., & Lopez, J. F. (2020). A Multispectral Camera Development: From the Prototype Assembly until Its Use in a UAV System. *Sensors*, 20(21), 6129. <https://doi.org/10.3390/s20216129>.
- Redmon Joseph, Santosh Divvala, Ross Girshick, & Ali Farhadi. (2016, August 6). You Only Look Once: Unified, Real-Time Object Detection. *Computer Vision Foundation*.
- Speth, S., Gonçalves, A., Rigault, B., Suzuki, S., Bouazizi, M., Matsuo, Y., & Prendinger, H. (2022). Deep learning with RGB and thermal images onboard a drone for monitoring operations. *Journal of Field Robotics*, 39(6), 840–868. <https://doi.org/10.1002/rob.22082>.
- Ultralytics YOLO8. (2024). Ultralytics YOLO Docs. Retrieved May 11, 2025, from <https://docs.ultralytics.com/models/yolo8/>.
- Verykokou, S., & Ioannidis, C. (2016). Exterior orientation estimation of oblique aerial imagery using vanishing point. *ISPRS - International Archives of the Photogrammetry, Remote Sensing and Spatial Information Sciences*, XLI-B3, 123–130. <https://doi.org/10.5194/isprsarchives-XLI-B3-123-2016>.